

Extended string playing techniques in electroacoustic music performance

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Abstract

This work examines how extended string playing techniques function as primary generators of electroacoustic design in the repertoire for strings and electronics. This perspective acquires particular relevance in the context of string instruments, given their expressive potential and historical-cultural weight. Rather than treating such techniques as ornamental or timbral effects, the study considers them structural compositional tools that actively shape instrumental writing, electroacoustic configuration, and modes of interaction in performance.

The central question concerns how the choice of specific extended string playing techniques shapes not only the conception of the instrumental part, but also the configuration of electronic resources and the design of performance conditions. In this perspective, the performing ensemble emerges as a compositional construct, giving rise to a specific *écriture électroacoustique*: instrumental gesture, bodily action, electronic processes and acoustic spaces form an integrated system in which sound production and signal transformation are mutually dependent.

Drawing on theories of musical instrumentality and ecosystemic approaches to musical interaction, the article proposes a typology distinguishing between two operational profiles of creative practitioners: the ‘composer-user’, who integrates existing technologies into refined musical systems, and the ‘composer-luthier’, who invents or customizes tools as part of the compositional act itself. Through selected case studies, this article shows how extended string playing techniques may redefine new forms of instrumentality within electroacoustic music practices, potentially transforming the performance setup into a hybrid assemblage in which mechanical, electroacoustic, and computational agencies operate as interconnected musical instruments in their own right.

1. Introduction

1.1. Research context and focus

In works belonging to the repertoire for strings and electronics, the particular relationship between acoustic and electroacoustic musical instruments decisively shapes compositional practice. This interaction becomes particularly significant when attention shifts to the evolving modes of sound production that, over time, have redefined both the expressive potential of string instruments and the role of the ‘virtuoso’ performer. In this context,

technology is understood not as a neutral medium but as a constitutive element of musical expression. This perspective acquires particular relevance in the context of string instruments, whose historically sedimented performance traditions intensify the implications of technological mediation. As modes of sound production evolve, both the sonic identity of the instrument and the cultural figure of the virtuoso are fundamentally reconfigured.

Against this background, the present study addresses three interrelated issues. First, it examines how historically grounded musical resources such as string instruments enter into dialogue with rapidly evolving electroacoustic and computer-music technologies, whose design paradigms and aesthetic orientations remain identifiable despite constant technological renewal. Second, extended techniques are considered not merely as ornamental elements but as structural compositional tools, often mediating between creative strategies and embodied performance modalities. Third, the study explores how the choice of specific extended techniques affects both the writing of instrumental parts and the configuration of the electronic setup. In many cases, these techniques directly condition what kinds of processing are possible, meaningful, or musically necessary.

Methodologically, this study adopts an analytical-comparative approach, combining close reading of scores, examination of electroacoustic configurations, and performance-based reflection. The selected case studies are interpreted not only as ‘works’ but as situated performance practices in which instrumental gesture and electroacoustic design are structurally interdependent.

1.2. Literature review

The present study builds upon three interconnected areas of research that converge on the question of extended instrumental techniques in electroacoustic music contexts. To frame this analysis, a first body of scholarship concerns extended string techniques and instrumental performance practice. Studies such as those by Patricia and Allen Strange (Strange and Strange 2001) clarify how physical gesture and unconventional sound-production methods reshape the sonic morphology of string instruments. These contributions are essential for understanding extended techniques not merely as technical deviations, but as embodied practices that expand the instrument’s expressive and structural potential.

A second theoretical strand addresses musical instrumentality. Philosophical and musicological reflections on what constitutes a musical instrument, including Alperson’s work (Alperson 2008), allow technological tools — analog devices, live electronics architectures, and computational processes — to be understood as musical instruments within performance practice rather than as neutral tools. This perspective is crucial for examining how electroacoustic setups participate actively in shaping musical form and interaction.

A third area involves ecological and ecosystemic approaches to musical interaction, particularly those exploring co-agency among performer, instrument, electronics, and acoustic space (Waters 2007, Di Scipio 2020). These frameworks provide the conceptual basis for understanding performance as a dynamic configuration in which multiple agencies interact within a shared environment. Recent research on live electronic performance practice further emphasizes the role of performers and technological mediation in shaping musical interaction (Toro Pérez et al. 2024).

An in-depth analytical survey of the repertoire for strings and electronics — beginning with musical works such as *Music for String Quartet and Tape* (string quartet and tape, 1957-1962) by Bulent Arel, *Analogique A/B* (nine stringed instruments and tape, 1958-1959) by Iannis Xenakis and *Capriccio* (violin and tape, 1959) by Henk Badings — provides the necessary perspective for situating the five works examined in this study. This repertoire is both rich and difficult to circumscribe. It includes major works distinguished not only by their linguistic and expressive originality in the use of musical resources — whether historically established or newly developed — but also by the diverse relationships they establish between musical means and practices bearing markedly different cultural connotations.

Although these thematic areas are not the primary focus of the present discussion, they collectively constitute the theoretical background supporting the case studies that follow. Within this framework, they serve to clarify the role of extended string techniques in selected works from this repertoire.

2. Conceptual framework: extended string playing techniques within the compositional design of performance conditions

Many composers working in mixed music have explored original forms of interaction between instrumental gesture and electronic processes. It seems appropriate to investigate whether the configuration of performance resources is itself an intrinsic part of compositional thought or merely a functional domain instrumental to particular musical goals. From this perspective, the ensemble of instrumental techniques, acoustic and spatial conditions, electroacoustic and computational resources involved in a performance can be understood as a *performance ecosystem*. This ecosystem is not neutral but results from deliberate compositional choices. It constitutes a hybrid assemblage in which instrumental gesture and electronic transformation are dynamically and structurally interdependent. In this study, the notion of performance ecosystem refers to a particularly high degree of structural cohesion among instrumental gesture, electroacoustic processes, and performance conditions, and may be understood as a limiting condition of interaction. Not all of the works discussed here realize such conditions to the same extent; rather, the concept serves as a reference model for assessing different degrees of integration.

Within this perspective, extended string playing techniques occupy a central role. A notion of extended performance techniques has been recently defined:

Techniques of instrumental and vocal performance aimed at expanding the expressive possibilities of traditional performing resources. These techniques are used and reworked when instruments are conceived not as generators of notes (sounds with definite pitch and uniform timbre), but as unprecedented dynamic sound sources, capable of producing multiple timbral and noise-based outcomes. Historically, extended performance techniques are part of the broader renewal of musical means in late modernity and contemporary times, alongside the expansion of orchestral resources, the valorization of percussion instruments, and the integration of electroacoustic and computer technologies. (Di Scipio 2025, pp.536-537)

As Hugh Davies has observed, the instrumentarium of Western music has historically been in continuous transformation, with modifications to instruments and playing techniques accompanying shifts in musical thought (Davies 2020). The twentieth century, in particular,

witnessed an unprecedented expansion of instrumental resources and experimental practice approaches.

The repertoire examined here may be understood as a further stage in this trajectory. Emerging from instrumental practice, extended string playing techniques function not as ornamental or purely timbral effects, but rather as structural articulation tools that condition both musical writing and performance practice. The choice of specific techniques frequently determines the types of real-time processing that are feasible, meaningful, or even necessary, thereby shaping the architecture of the electroacoustic and computer processing setup itself. This perspective reveals a compositional and functional orientation that directly involves the invention and exploration of performance conditions. The boundaries between composition and performance consequently become porous, converging into a single creative continuum.

This shift foregrounds instrumental and technical invention as a compositional gesture closely linked to performative practice, implying the necessity «to invent the tools of one’s own expression» (Fleuret 1988; Alessandretti et al. 2021). In order to articulate distinct modes of engagement with these performance conditions, two operational typologies of creative practitioners can be proposed: the *composer-user* and the *composer-luthier*. Composer-users integrate existing technologies expressively, often with the support of technical experts to pursue their musical aims. On the other hand, composer-luthiers set out to shape their own original (if not idiosyncratic) tools – be them mechanical, electroacoustic or computational – as an integral part of their creative practice. In such cases, instrument-making becomes integral of musical invention itself.

The distinction proposed here is not intended as an ontological classification but as a heuristic model. It identifies positions along a spectrum rather than fixed categories, since both tendencies may coexist within a single artistic trajectory. In many cases, its purpose is analytical rather than taxonomical: it clarifies how technological invention or appropriation functions within specific performance conditions¹. The following tables (Figure 1) provide a conceptual map illustrating how certain works embody these operational configurations, with particular attention to the role of extended string techniques in relation to live electronic processes.

<i>Composer-luthier examples</i>	Compositional practice context	<i>Composer-user examples</i>	Compositional practice context
Jon Phetteplace - <i>Displacements</i> (cello, microphones and mixer photocell divider 1967) David Behrman - <i>Cello with melody-driven electronics</i> (cello and interactive-analog devices, 1974)	Improvisational practices inside experimental collectives. (Musica Elettronica Viva; Sonic Arts Union)	Jonathan Harvey - <i>Adanya</i> (cello, electronic keyboard and live electronics, 1994) Kajja Saariaho - <i>Folia</i> (double bass and live electronics, 1995)	Extended techniques and electronics processes for composing spectra
Michelangelo Lupone - <i>Altair</i> (violin, tape and live electronics, 1986) Grégoire Lorieux - <i>Passage de la lumière</i> (string quartet and live electronics, 1986) Giorgio Klauer - <i>Tre aspetti del tempo</i> (hyperviolin and live electronics, 2007)	Interest in creating correlations between electronic processes and instrumental gestures	Pierre Boulez - <i>Anthèmes II</i> (violin and live electronics, 1997) Ivan Fedele - <i>Elettra</i> (viola and live electronics, 1999) Philippe Manoury - <i>Tensio</i> (string quartet and live electronics, 2010)	Motivic expansion of both instrumental gesture and electronics
Karlheinz Essl - <i>Da braccio</i> (any stringed instrument, computer and live electronics, 1999-2000) Mari Kimura - <i>U (The Cormorant)</i> (violin or Zeta violin and live interactive system, 1991)	Practices related to interactivity	Georg Friedrich Haas - <i>String quartet N°7</i> (string quartet and live electronics, 2012)	Micropolyphony as instrumental and electronic tool

Figure 1: Some examples of the composer-luthier and composer-user paradigms.

¹ It is not uncommon to find examples in which a rather standardized approach is pursued: the composer acts as a skilled user of commercially available technologies, relying on expressive codes more closely aligned with conventional musical languages, while drawing on a background shaped by the development of new instrument and practices.

On the left side, the works listed by composers such as Jon Phetteplace, David Behrman, Grégoire Lorieux, or Karlheinz Essl exemplify a luthier-oriented approach in which technological design becomes integral to the compositional act. Those on the right, by composers such as Pierre Boulez, Kaija Saariaho, Philippe Manoury, and Georg Friedrich Haas, illustrate an expert-user orientation: the tools pre-exist and are absorbed as idiomatic compositional resources. This spectrum allows the case studies to be contextualized in terms of specific operational configurations rather than fixed authorial identities.

3. Case studies overview

The conceptual framework outlined above provides the criteria for selecting and interpreting the following case studies. An extensive analytical survey of the repertoire for strings and electronics reveals a number of works in which either the development of specific instrumental techniques — or the very construction of acoustic, electroacoustic, or computational instruments — assumes a central compositional role (Boccio 2025). In such cases, the compositional design of performance resources directly determines the performative practice required for the realization of the work. These case studies have been selected within this perspective. They exemplify situations in which a strong correlation emerges between compositional strategy and performance conditions, resulting in a significant convergence of compositional and performative domains. In these works, extended string playing techniques function not as effects but as syntactic and structural agents, particularly when integrated with live signal processing.

The production of composers such as Jean-Claude Risset (1938-2016), Denis Dufour (1953), Agostino Di Scipio (1962), Clara Iannotta (1983), and Luc Döbereiner (1984) belonging to different generations and aesthetic premises, exemplify distinct positions along the spectrum between composer-luthier and composer-user. Nevertheless, they share a strong interest in the central role of instrumental gesture, establishing — in a different way required by each piece — a close and mature relationship between different approaches to live sound processing and instrumental action, ranging from relatively established techniques to highly experimental configurations². The selected paradigmatic case studies that follow aim to analyse how, in each case, extended string playing techniques contribute to redefining both instrumentality and the electroacoustic performance configuration, with extended techniques operating as generative compositional tools.

The following case studies are organized according to the operational configuration embodied by each work, rather than following a chronological or generational sequence. The progression moves from configurations that remain closer to a composer-user paradigm — such as *dead wasps in the jam-jar (iii)* by Iannotta and, in a different way, *Pli de perversion/I* by Dufour, where technological tools are integrated within a defined instrumental framework — through the intermediate case of Risset's *Variants*, in which performer-driven innovation reshapes digital processing strategies, toward works such as Döbereiner's *Spur* and Di Scipio's *Two sound pieces for repertoire string music*, where the compositional act extends decisively into the design of interactive systems and performance ecosystems.

² In some cases, the act of constructing or customizing instruments and electronic systems becomes inseparable from compositional invention. In others, existing technologies are appropriated and reconfigured in highly idiomatic ways.

3.1. *dead wasps in the jam-jar (iii)* (2017-2018) by Clara Iannotta

In *dead wasps in the jam-jar (iii)* (2017–2018), composed for prepared string quartet and live electronics for the Arditti Quartet, Clara Iannotta seeks to expand the expressive possibilities of string instruments through physical preparation. The work represents a further development of ideas already explored in two preceding pieces³, and is structurally informed by materials derived from the *Double* and the *Courante* of Johann Sebastian Bach's Partita No. 1 in B minor for solo violin. A series of harmonic glissandi, circular bowing and differentiated right-hand pressures between *alto sul tasto* (AST) and *molto sul ponticello* (MSP), combined with the physical preparation of the instruments, articulates and enriches the structural skeleton of the Bach material. Each instrument is prepared with small everyday objects such as paper clips, hairpins, and rubber bands, which interfere with the normal vibration of the strings and significantly increase spectral complexity, as shown in Figure 2. The score prescribes the insertion of up to four circular metal paper clips per instrument, positioned strategically either near the fingerboard or close to the bridge (Iannotta 2018). This preparation takes on structural value: the bow must always pass between the clips, constraining the performer within a reduced physical space. The gesture is limited, yet the resulting spectral richness is amplified, functioning analogously to a filtering process.

Figure 2: An example of instrumental preparation in *dead wasps in the jam-jar (iii)*

The differentiated use of mutes made of rubber, metal, or wood for each instrument produces also a stratified system of timbral filtering. Combined with variable left-hand pressure ranging from ordinary stopping to extremely light harmonic touch, this generates a complex sound rich in inharmonicity and noise components, gradually distancing itself from traditional instrumental identity and approaching an electronic texture dimension. The resulting sonic world is unstable yet extremely detailed, making audible the micro-instabilities of friction, air, and resistance that usually remain hidden. Bow pressure becomes an autonomous timbral parameter, ranging from “almost no pressure” to overpressure (Iannotta 2018). The saturation produced by overpressure, especially when combined with the metallic preparation, creates acoustic distortions perceptually analogous to digital clipping or signal saturation, establishing a perceptual bridge toward the electronic layer. Micro-gestures derived from bow

³ These works include *dead wasps in the jam-jar (i)* for solo violin (2014–15), written for the violinist Yuki Numata Resnick, and *dead wasps in the jam-jar (ii)* for string orchestra and electronics (2016).

changes, circular bowing, rustling sounds, and subtle pressure shifts contribute to a collective texture that already suggests electroacoustic sensitivity even before the electronic part enters.

Iannotta's notational approach reflects a conception of sound as the outcome of independent gestural vectors. At several points in the score (Figure 3), the right-hand and left-hand actions are radically separated. A dedicated graphic staff indicates the continuous position of the bow between AST and MSP, represented as morphological trajectories through zigzag lines. Gesture is thus treated as a dynamic continuum rather than as a series of discrete articulations.

Figure 3: Clara Iannotta, *dead wasps in the jam-jar (iii)*, excerpt from the published score (Edition Peters).

The relationship with the electronic part is not dialectical but mimetic. The electronics consist exclusively of sine waves generated through a Max/MSP patch. The pure sinusoid, as the elementary component of all complex periodic sounds, both contrasts with and complements the noisy, spectrally complex texture of the prepared strings. The sine waves are triggered via MIDI pedal or keyboard by the cellist and function as spectral residues or shadows of the high-frequency components produced by extended techniques such as col legno tratto or artificial harmonics. The composer recommends amplification of the instruments and connection to a stereo system in order to facilitate blending. Amplification contributes to reveal inner noises and instabilities, reinforcing the perception of the quartet as a single, breathing organism.

In *dead wasps in the jam-jar (iii)*, extended techniques do not serve to enhance performers' virtuosity but to erode timbral purity to the point of near indistinguishability from electronic processes. The electronics do not transform the acoustic sound; rather, the acoustic sound, through preparation and overpressure, transforms itself into something electronically analogous. These gestures are not conceived as effects. Each bow movement determines the

structural density of the texture and becomes a formal articulating device. The use of preparatory objects is justified not as theatrical intervention but as the only means capable of physically realizing the sonic image envisioned by the composer.

3.2. *Pli de perversion/1* (1978) by Denis Dufour

Following the teachings of Ivo Malec and, above all, Pierre Schaeffer — of whom he later became assistant — Denis Dufour composed *Pli de perversion/1* (also known as *Velours des dunes infoulées*) between September and October 1978 at the Conservatoire national supérieur de musique et de danse de Paris. The work represents a paradigmatic example of the application of acousmatic principles directly to instrumental writing. Conceived for one string instrument and one synthesis device (both under the performer's choice), it is the first piece in the *Pli de perversion* cycle⁴, from which subsequent works would progressively emerge⁵. The piece was written for violinist Laurent Cuniot and electronic musician Yann Geslin⁶.

In this composition, Dufour abandons traditional notation in favor of a graphic score functioning as a cartography of dominant sound characteristics, effectively prescribing timbral morphology rather than pitch structures. The vertical axis of the score provides an approximate indication of instrumental register, ranging from low to high, while the horizontal axis represents proportional time. The crucial element for understanding the role of extended techniques lies in the explanatory legend, where Dufour explicitly acknowledges his theoretical lineage: “The symbols used all refer to the *Traité des objets musicaux* by Pierre Schaeffer” (Dufour 1978). Consequently, bow technique is not prescribed through conventional instrumental indications such as *sul ponticello* or *col legno*, but must be inferred by the performer in order to realize specific morphological demands.

As illustrated in Figure 4, the notation is intentionally schematic, requiring the performer to enrich the informational content of the score through active timbral variation and detailed shaping of sonic matter. This stimulates a mode of listening-based performance practice. The series of works explore a form of interaction between instrumental gesture and electronic sound within a setting comparable to a chamber duo. In this first piece, however, the two instruments are treated relatively independently, with the synthesizer largely assuming a discreet accompanying role within an overall restrained dynamic framework.

⁴ The cycle, in turn, is part of a larger series of works entitled *Fantaisies romantiques et baroques*.

⁵ Among the works that can be associated with the repertoire under examination is *Pli de perversion/2* (also known as *Ourlé du lac*), a 1984 piece written for violin, synthesizer, and the SYTER system. The latter is a real-time digital signal processing device developed at the Ina-GRM by Jean-François Allouis and his collaborators; after approximately ten years of development, it was used in a performative context for the first time by Dufour himself on the occasion of the premiere of this work.

⁶ At the suggestion of François Bayle, Dufour founded in 1977, together with Yann Geslin, the Trio GRM Plus, the first ensemble of synthesizer dedicated to contemporary repertoire. The group later evolved into the ensemble TM+, with Laurent Cuniot among its founding members.

Figure 4: Denis Dufour, *Pli de perversion/I*, excerpt from the score (author's manuscript).

The score classifies several types of attack transients, according to energetic profile and envelope rather than conventional dynamic markings. This forces the performer to recalibrate right-hand technique, particularly in bow management. Categories such as *Abrupte*, *Molle*, *Plate*, and *Douce* demand differentiated control of bow pressure and speed, shifting attention from pitch articulation to morphological shaping. Extended technique here becomes a direct translation of acousmatic categories into embodied gesture.

Another significant parameter is the *Texture de masse*. Through graphic notation, Dufour specifies profiles of spectral density, directing the instrument toward noisy or inharmonic territories. While *Son tonique* and *Groupe tonique* refer to harmonic or predominantly harmonic spectra, indications such as *Son nodal*, *Groupe nodal*, and *Frange* prescribe the gradual predominance of non-harmonic partials or spectral saturation. These effects are technically realized through harmonics, varying degrees of bow pressure ranging from complex 'flutelike' sounds to overpressure, and extreme contact points near the bridge or fingerboard. The category of *Grains* translates Schaeffer's notion of sonic grain into instrumental terms: friction becomes a perceptible textural unit, transforming bow contact into controlled noise articulation. A *gros grain*, in contrast to a *grain fin*, intensifies mechanical friction by reducing bow speed and increasing pressure until individual bow-hair interactions emerge as audible micro-events (scratches).

The electronic component does not function as mere accompaniment but as a resonant and timbral extension of the instrument, with the synthesizer performer acting as an active partner. The synthesis device is required to possess "strong resonance", suggesting a signal treatment that expands the acoustic envelope into a symbiotic relationship. Electronics operate as an acoustic shadow in which extended bow techniques — noises, harmonics, airy sounds — find their synthetic counterpart in filtered textures.

Although the piece assumes a 'concertante' character, it simultaneously retains a chamber dimension. Temporal organization is governed by proportional notation (1 cm = 2 seconds), and performers are instructed not to seek strict second-by-second synchronization but rather an "order of proportional magnitude." This approach grants flexibility in adapting extended techniques while preserving musical breath. Analysis of the score reveals morphological symmetries: synthesizer lines often mirror or duplicate the intonational and mass profiles of the string instrument, reinforcing moments of sonic cohesion between acoustic and electronic

layers. Sound diffusion is entrusted to a third performer in order to maintain the “private and restrained character” prescribed by Dufour (Dufour 1978).

In *Pli de perversion/1*, extended techniques are structurally embedded in the musical form through the reciprocal feeding relationship between the bow player’s gesture and the synthesizer performer’s gesture. The synthesizer mirrors the timbral properties generated by bow friction, translating them into formally significant resonances. It reacts to glissandi, bow pressure variations, and harmonic instability, producing a continuous folding of acoustic and synthetic layers. Each gesture generates a new timbral inflection within this dynamic interplay. Extended techniques thus emerge as the necessary consequence of a compositional writing that privileges mass and sonic morphology over pitch.

3.3. *Variants* (1994) by Jean Claude Risset

An exemplary case of reciprocal influence between technical and musical expertise is *Variants*, composed in 1994 by Jean-Claude Risset for the violinist and composer Mari Kimura and premiered at the 1994 Helsinki Festival. The work is central to this discussion because it presents a distinctive model of interaction between extended instrumental techniques and real-time digital processing, while also illustrating a collaborative dynamic between a composer-luthier who acts here as an ‘expert-user’ and a performer whose instrumental innovations directly shaped the compositional design. Beyond his role as a pioneer of computer music, Risset is widely known for his research into psychoacoustic paradoxes, including the so-called Shepard–Risset glissando, a continuous version of the Shepard scale that produces the illusion of an endlessly ascending (or descending) pitch. This auditory illusion informs also the realization of *Variants*. Through delayed pitch transpositions generated by a harmonizer, the layered violin sound is perceived as continuously rising and falling, creating a dynamic instability that resonates with Risset’s broader psychoacoustic investigations.

The title *Variants* refers both to the real-time digital transformations applied to the violin sound — such as pitch transposition, delay, and reverberation — and to internal processes of micro-variation embedded within the violin part itself. Temporal intervals between melodic groups function as evolving rhythmic units, gradually transforming over time. These micro-variations interact with a specific extended bowing technique developed by Kimura: the production of subharmonics (Kimura 1995). Risset was the first composer to use Kimura’s pioneering subharmonic technique explicitly, aside from Kimura in her own works (Kimura 2006). Subharmonics allows the performer to produce pitches below the open G string without retuning the instrument. The technique demands extremely refined control of bow pressure, speed, and angle. In *Variants*, subharmonics do not function as occasional special effects but as one of the core generative principles of the composition. The expanded pitch range made possible by this technique provides the acoustic material upon which the electronic transformations operate.

The electronic component reacts directly to the violin’s sound. The original version was realized using an Ensoniq DP/4 multi-effect digital signal processor, an advanced commercial device at the time. The entire electronic structure was later migrated to Max/MSP, and in the revised version of 2004–2007 Kimura herself implemented the processes within a dedicated

Max patch⁷. Risset employs real-time digital transformations — particularly frequency transpositions through the use of a harmonizer, along with delay and reverberation — to construct a contrapuntal and harmonic texture that extends the violin line according to an orchestrational logic. While the writing of the violin part remains relatively traditional, the electronic layer unfolds as a spatial and harmonic extension of the performer’s gestures. Crucially, this electronic fabric emerges directly from the violinist’s timing and articulation. Variations in the temporal spacing of melodic groups generate perceptual phenomena such as *stream segregation*: intervals that function melodically in the acoustic domain become rhythmic patterns when electronically transformed. The electronics therefore do not merely process the violin sound; they reveal hidden rhythmic and harmonic structures embedded within the gesture itself, bringing them to perceptual prominence. The live processing acquires an orchestrative dimension, particularly through the extensive use of the harmonizer.

The work also integrates psychoacoustic illusion at a structural level. In *Variants*, such effects arise from the interaction between Kimura’s subharmonic technique and precise real-time digital transformations. The illusion of continuous ascent or descent becomes inseparable from the performer’s bow control.

From the perspective of performance practice, *Variants* exemplifies a gesture-centric configuration: the violinist’s extended bowing technique drives the electronics, while the electronic response reshapes the listener’s perception of the gesture. The instrument is extended simultaneously in physical, spectral, and perceptual terms. Subharmonics function as an engine for real-time digital transformation, merging acoustic precision with psychoacoustic design. For these reasons, *Variants* occupies a significant place within a broader lineage of works in which compositional thinking emerges from the interdependence between instrumental gesture and electronic processing.

3.4. *Spur* (2019) by Luc Döbereiner

Spur is a composition for cello, double bass, and live electronics written in 2019 by Luc Döbereiner between Berlin and Graz and dedicated to the Ensemble Schallfeld. Döbereiner’s artistic research spans multiple areas, including timbral investigation through both conventional and unconventional performance techniques, improvisational practices, and more recent explorations of AI as a compositional tool⁸.

The work unfolds through the interaction of two sonic streams in continuous and gradual transformation. This interaction operates on multiple levels: on the one hand within the physical acoustic space, concerning the live projection of instrumental and electronic sounds; on the other within a “digitally augmented” space (Döbereiner 2019), made possible by the specific listening systems employed and by the performers’ perceptual engagement with electronically mediated sound. The instrumental writing is structured around three interrelated sound morphologies organized according to increasing or decreasing spectral complexity: harmonics, hybrid sounds between harmonics and multiphonics, and multiphonics. Transitions between these categories occur without interruption, supporting an exploratory

⁷ In the revised version, harmonizer voices are used more extensively, with independent transposition and delay implemented in Max. On the interdependence between instrumental writing and digital signal processing in *Variants*, see (Dülger 2015).

⁸ Such a diversity of interests may be regarded as a characteristic condition of many composers belonging to more recent generations.

approach to instrumental sound. No moments of total silence are prescribed; instead, all instrumental and electronic variations unfold with extreme gradualness: in this context, extended string playing techniques function as generative structural devices. They determine the spectral content analyzed in real time and thus directly shape the behavior of the electroacoustic system.

Real-time signal processing is based on C++ and SuperCollider code that independently analyzes the sounds produced by the cello and double bass, extracting spectral data used to control oscillators. The resulting frequencies are processed and distributed both through loudspeakers and via bone-conduction headphones worn by the performers. Through the headphones, each performer primarily hears the electronic outcomes derived from the other instrumentalist rather than from their own sound, responding to them in real time. This mechanism establishes a form of cross-listening in which concentrated auditory attention becomes a structural component of performance practice. The electronic system does not merely extend the instrument but actively redefines the conditions of interaction.

In certain sections, the system generates frequencies not directly present in the instrumental material at the moment of analysis but emerging from its spectral treatment. The electronics thus operate as an unstable harmonic reference, influenced by parameters such as the number of oscillators, the duration of partials, pauses, and threshold values. A process of reciprocal conditioning emerges among performers and system, and the final sonic outcome remains contingent upon the interplay between instrumental gesture, analysis processes, room acoustics, and technological configuration both electroacoustic and computational.

Figure 5: Luc Döbereiner, *Spur*, excerpt from the score (author's edition).

The notation proves functional in relation to the processes and gestures involved. As shown in Figure 5, each instrument is notated on two staves: the lower staff indicates finger positions lightly touching the strings, while the upper staff specifies the expected harmonic partials.

Dynamics are represented through graphic elements suggesting amplitude, while parameters such as bow pressure, speed, and position are not rigidly prescribed but entrusted to the performer's sensitivity. The score thus conveys gestural intention without overdetermination, ensuring that dynamic and timbral transitions remain idiomatic to the physical possibilities of the instrument.

In the improvisatory sections, indicated by a large arrow in the score (Figure 5), performers must observe the prescribed duration and maintain timbral continuity with adjacent sections. Within these constraints, they may select, transpose, and order pitches derived from the spectral material heard in the headphones, avoiding abrupt discontinuities or bow changes and responding to the densification or rarefaction of the electronic texture. Particularly significant are the passages in which the electronics are absent. Here, performers are required to alter execution conditions more radically, especially in bow management, in order to produce increased spectral complexity. The attempt to control sonic outcomes does not eliminate unpredictability but incorporates it as an integral element of the compositional design.

In *Spur*, sound is thus conceived as an unstable event, suspended between determinism and indeterminism, emerging from the dynamic relationship between instrumental gesture, electroacoustic setup, and heightened listening. In this configuration, extended techniques do not merely generate spectral material; they actively regulate the feedback conditions of the electroacoustic system. Instrumental gesture becomes a parameter within a distributed network of computational and spatial interactions, reinforcing the notion of instrumentality as relational rather than object-based.

3.5. *Two sound pieces for repertoire string music* (2012) by Agostino Di Scipio

In *Two sound pieces for repertoire string music* (for any number of string instruments and live electronics, 2012), Agostino Di Scipio reshapes, albeit through different procedures, several operational principles characteristic of his earlier works⁹. The piece employs real-time digital signal processing with feedback mechanisms — implemented in two alternative DSP environments (Kyma or Pure Data) — that route the instrumental signal across delay loops, samplers, granulators, and filtering processes. The parameters of these processes react to the acoustic conditions of the performance space and to a limited vocabulary of instrumental gestures derived from extended techniques, precisely specified in the score (Di Scipio 2012). Within this 'chamber music-like' context, the instruments do not merely function as sound generators; they exert direct control over the electronic processing, whose outcomes in turn influence instrumental gesture. A systemic feedback configuration thus emerges, operating across multiple structural levels of the musical form. The acoustics of the performance space assume a decisive role, both expressively and constructively. Performance is conceived as a dynamic network of interactions specific to the environment, the electroacoustic and computational setup, and the instrumental gestures themselves.

At least two instrumental performers are required. Each one independently selects short fragments from the traditional repertoire of their instrument, whether solo or chamber music,

⁹ In *Plex* (double bass and quadraphonic support, 1991), a limited number of instrumental gestures undergo subtle micro-variations, mirrored in the processed sound materials on the fixed support. Beginning with *5 interazioni cicliche alle differenze sensibili* (string quartet and digital signal processing devices, 1997–98), Di Scipio increasingly adopts real-time processing procedures that evolve in relation to a contained vocabulary of extended playing techniques.

and performs them according to compositional constraints established by Di Scipio. These fragments are executed using only the left hand, without the bow or with the bow managed independently. Their musical origin becomes aurally unrecognizable: original relationships of dynamics, articulation, tempo, and duration are suppressed, while only the sequence of pitches remains intact. In the second section of the work, for example, each performer executes the chosen material through techniques aimed at its deconstruction, particularly through various forms of tapping (with or without bow, and ricochet), *col legno*, and *battuto* (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Some selected tapping techniques characteristic of *Two Sound Pieces for String Repertoire*, excerpt from the score (author's edition).

A further distinctive feature lies in the use of the instruments as resonators. The selected repertoire fragments are reproduced through small audio playback devices, placing an earbud directly on the soundboard. Additionally, each instrument is equipped with a miniature condenser microphone inserted through the f-holes and fixed inside the resonant body. The instrument thus becomes both a site of signal acquisition and a space of listening, capturing sound produced by the performer as well as audio playback filtered through the soundboard. This model is applied to each instrument involved. The results produced by the loudspeaker system further contribute to the configuration of the setup, which is governed by a computational architecture capable of managing a complex network of dynamic relationships among sound, space, body, and machine. These mechanisms generate a dense network of interdependencies that remain highly sensitive to all variables present in the performance ecosystem.

Figure 7 clarifies how these processes are recursively interconnected: delay loops, samplers, granular and filtering mechanisms are not independent but form a closed feedback network in which processed sound re-enters the system through microphones, soundboard, and loudspeakers, and whose parameters are modulated in real time according to the spectral and dynamic characteristics of the instrumental signal. Although each process, considered individually, is relatively simple, their serial concatenation and constant interaction among microphones, soundboard, and loudspeakers produce significant timbral variance. The resulting configuration is a nonlinear system that demands from the performer a high degree of awareness of their spatial and sonic agency. Execution cannot be reduced to the mechanical reproduction of gestures, given the tight interdependence of all performative resources.

Figure 7: The performance ecosystem that generates sound and regulates the dynamic relationships among its various components.

In Di Scipio's work, extended playing techniques represent only one component within a broader generative system. These performance ecosystems function effectively only under conditions of interaction and timbral cohesion among all elements involved: instruments, electroacoustic and computational configuration, and acoustic space. The performer is therefore required not only to manage micro-variations of gesture and dynamics with musical sensitivity, but above all to cultivate a refined capacity for listening, capable of perceiving the relationships between produced sounds and the responses of both environment and processing system. Within this network of interactions, and through the use of specific extended techniques, the selected repertoire fragments ultimately become distant traces, less quotations than residues of historical memory, more faded echoes than carriers of recognizable musical meaning. In this context, extended techniques function less as virtuosic expansions and more as regulatory inputs within a nonlinear ecosystem. The work exemplifies a compositional model in which the design of conditions precedes and determines the sonic outcome.

4. Conclusions

The analyses presented in this study demonstrate that, within the repertoire for strings and electronics, extended string playing techniques operate not as peripheral embellishments but as structural and generative principles. Across different aesthetic orientations and technological contexts, these techniques repeatedly function as mediating agents between instrumental writing and electroacoustic design, shaping both sonic outcomes and the architecture of performance conditions.

A consistent redefinition of instrumentality emerges across the case studies. In Iannotta, instrumental preparation and controlled bow pressure dissolve the boundary between acoustic friction and electronic synthesis. In Dufour, acousmatic morphology is translated into embodied technique, compelling performers to derive gesture from spectral prescriptions. In Risset, subharmonics — developed here in close collaboration with Mari Kimura — become the acoustic engine of real-time digital transformation, demonstrating how performer-driven innovation conditions compositional form. In Döbereiner, cross-listening and spectral analysis

generate a dynamically unstable system in which gesture and processing mutually reshape one another. In Di Scipio, extended techniques operate within a nonlinear feedback configuration where instrument, space, electroacoustic and computational processes co-constitute a performative ecosystem that determines the sonic result.

Despite their differences, these works share a structural trait: the configuration of performance resources is inseparable from compositional thought. The electroacoustic setup does not merely amplify or process pre-existing instrumental material; it is co-determined by the choice of extended techniques. In many instances, specific processing strategies become meaningful — or even technically feasible — only in relation to particular modes of sound production. Often, what is designed and tested are not autonomous works in the traditional sense, but situated performance practices. The distinction between composer-user and composer-luthier proves useful not as a rigid taxonomy but as a heuristic tool for mapping this spectrum of practices. The case studies show that both operational profiles converge around a shared concern: the invention, adaptation, or critical appropriation of technological tools as part of the compositional act. Technological mediation is thus absorbed into musical thought rather than treated as a neutral support.

From a broader historical perspective, this repertoire reveals a gradual displacement of the virtuoso paradigm. Technical mastery no longer resides in pitch-centered complexity but in the refined control of friction, pressure, spectral instability, feedback, and perceptual illusion. The performer becomes a regulator of energetic flows within a hybrid assemblage of acoustic, electronic, and computational agencies. Listening assumes a structural function, serving as an active condition for maintaining systemic balance. In this expanded framework, the composer increasingly operates as a designer of conditions, shaping the relational field in which instrumental gesture and technological mediation unfold.

Ultimately, extended string playing techniques mark a shift from instrument as object to instrument as relational field. The string instrument is no longer conceived as an autonomous sound source interacting externally with electronics, but as one node within a distributed network of transformations. In this sense, the electroacoustic performance configuration can be understood as a hybrid instrument in its own right — an assemblage sustained through continuous negotiation between gesture, signal, space, and machine. Rather than negating historical instrumentality, these practices reactivate it under new technological conditions, giving rise to a composite instrumentality in which composition, performance, and technological design converge into a single creative continuum.

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